

AN IMPROVED ANALYSIS OF THE MODE I CRACK OPENING DISPLACEMENT OF CFRP-DCB SPECIMENS

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ABSTRACT

An analytical model was developed for mode I interlaminar fracture in double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens of unidirectional CFRP laminates. Crack opening displacements predicted with the model are found to be in good agreement with those experimentally observed by moire interferometry. It is also demonstrated that the material deformability ahead of the crack front makes an important contribution to increasing the values of crack opening displacement, specimen compliance and fracture toughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The double cantilever beam (DCB) test has been widely used to study mode I interlaminar fracture of composite materials. Fracture toughness of DCB specimens is usually evaluated using a built-in cantilever beam model which assumes zero slope and displacement at the crack tip, i.e. the beam root of the specimen. However, it has been suggested that material deformability ahead of the crack tip plays an important role in the evaluation of fracture toughness and that this should be taken into account in the analysis [1-4].

The purpose of the present work was to study this problem for DCB specimens of unidirectional CFRP composites. An analytical model was developed for analyzing crack opening displacement (COD) as a function of material stiffness ahead of the crack front. To establish the validity of the present COD solution, comparison was made with experimental results determined in the vicinity of the crack tip using moire interferometry [5]. Results are also presented for the effect of the material stiffness on the determination of specimen compliance and fracture toughness. An attempt was made to clarify the discrepancy between the built-in cantilever beam analysis and the present approach.

2. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

2.1. Basic Equations

As a basic analytical model for DCB specimens, we employed a finite length beam which is partly free and partly supported by an elastic foundation as illustrated in Fig.1. Kanninen [1]

analyzed this model and obtained the following expressions for the beam deflection $w(x)$ at the two intervals $(-a \leq x \leq 0)$ and $(0 \leq x \leq c)$, where the x is placed coincident with the beam axis and its origin is located at the left-hand end of the elastic foundation (see Fig.1)

$$w(x) = \frac{6P}{E_1 B H^3 \lambda^3} \begin{cases} \frac{\lambda^3 x^3}{3} + a \lambda^3 x^2 - A \lambda x + B, & -a \leq x \leq 0 \\ a \lambda \sin \lambda x \operatorname{Sinh} \lambda x - \left(\frac{A-1}{2}\right) \sin \lambda x \operatorname{Cosh} \lambda x + \\ + B \cos \lambda x \operatorname{Cosh} \lambda x - \left(\frac{A+1}{2}\right) \cos \lambda x \operatorname{Sinh} \lambda x, & 0 \leq x \leq c \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where

$$A = \left[\frac{\operatorname{Sinh}^2 \lambda c + \sin^2 \lambda c}{\operatorname{Sinh}^2 \lambda c - \sin^2 \lambda c} \right] + 2a \lambda \left[\frac{\operatorname{Sinh} \lambda c \operatorname{Cosh} \lambda c + \sin \lambda c \cos \lambda c}{\operatorname{Sinh}^2 \lambda c - \sin^2 \lambda c} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$B = \left[\frac{\operatorname{Sinh} \lambda c \operatorname{Cosh} \lambda c - \sin \lambda c \cos \lambda c}{\operatorname{Sinh}^2 \lambda c - \sin^2 \lambda c} \right] + a \lambda \left[\frac{\operatorname{Sinh}^2 \lambda c + \sin^2 \lambda c}{\operatorname{Sinh}^2 \lambda c - \sin^2 \lambda c} \right]$$

$$\lambda = [3k / E_1 B H^3]^{1/4} \quad (3)$$

and E_1 is the axial modulus, B is the beam width, H is the beam thickness, and k is the extensional stiffness of the foundation (see Fig.1).

Fig.1 Basic model for the present analysis

2.2. Crack Opening Displacement Analysis

In the present study, Kanninen's solution (1) was used to analyze the COD profile in the vicinity of the crack tip, i.e. the beam root of the DCB specimen as illustrated in Fig.2. To simplify the present analysis, it is assumed that the uncracked region of the specimen is long enough so that the influence of the crack on the free-end of the specimen is negligible. Under such an assumption, and for the case of $\lambda c > 2\pi$, all the bracketed terms in eq.(2) can be approximately equated to unity, thus we obtain

Fig.2 Schematic displacements around a crack tip of a DCB specimen

$$A = 1 + 2a\lambda, \quad B = 1 + a\lambda \quad (4)$$

Substituting eq.(4) into eq.(1), we obtain the following expressions for the beam deflection $w(x)$

$$w(x) = \frac{2P}{E_1BH^3} \begin{cases} (3a+x)x^2 - \frac{6a}{\lambda} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2a\lambda}\right)x + \frac{3a}{\lambda^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{a\lambda}\right), & -a \leq x \leq 0 \\ \frac{3a}{\lambda^2} \left[\left(1 + \frac{1}{a\lambda}\right) \cos\lambda x - \sin\lambda x \right] e^{-\lambda x}, & 0 \leq x \leq c \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Using eq.(5) for the midplane deflection of half of the specimen thickness as illustrated in Fig.2, and assuming zero crack opening displacement at the crack tip, we employ the following expression for the COD profile of the DCB specimen

$$COD(r) = \frac{4P}{E_1BH^3} \left[(3a-r)r^2 + \frac{6a}{\lambda} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2a\lambda}\right)r + \frac{3a}{\lambda^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{a\lambda}\right)(1 - e^{-\lambda r}) \right], \quad \theta = \pi \quad (6)$$

where r and θ represent the cylindrical polar coordinates as shown in Fig.2. Equation (6) is shown to satisfy the continuity condition at the crack tip $r=0$ and the boundary condition at the loading point $r=a$. It should be noted that for the infinite value of λ , i.e. $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, eq.(6) is identical to the built-in cantilever beam relationship given by

$$COD(r) = \frac{4P}{E_1BH^3} (3a-r)r^2 \quad (7)$$

A cursory examination of eq.(6) reveals that for finite values of λ the present solution (6) gives larger value of COD than eq.(7).

2.3. Compliance and Fracture Toughness Analysis

The mode I fracture toughness can be determined from the following equation

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (8)$$

where C is the specimen compliance given by

$$C = COD(a)/P \quad (9)$$

Substituting eq.(6) into eq.(9), and neglecting the exponential term appearing in the equation, we obtain

$$C = \frac{COD(a)}{P} = \frac{4}{E_1BH^3} \left[2a^3 + \frac{6}{\lambda} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2a\lambda} \right) a^2 + \frac{3}{\lambda^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{a\lambda} \right) a \right] \quad (10)$$

$$= C_B \left(1 + \frac{3}{a\lambda} + \frac{3}{a^2\lambda^2} + \frac{3}{2a^3\lambda^3} \right)$$

where

$$C_B = \frac{8a^3}{E_1BH^3} \quad (11)$$

Differentiating eq.(10) with respect to the crack length a , and substituting into eq.(8), we obtain the fracture toughness expression as follows

$$G_I = G_{IB} \left(1 + \frac{2}{a\lambda} + \frac{1}{a^2\lambda^2} \right) \quad (12)$$

where G_{IB} is given by

$$G_{IB} = \frac{12P^2a^2}{E_1B^2H^3} \quad (13)$$

For the infinite value of λ , i.e. $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, the solutions (10) and (12) are identical to the cantilever beam relationships which are given by eqs.(11) and (13), respectively. For a finite value of λ , however, it is shown that the present solutions give larger values of compliance and fracture toughness than eqs.(11) and (13).

3. COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Experimental Procedure

The DCB test was performed on unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy composites as shown in Fig.3. The COD profile in the vicinity of the crack-tip was measured using moire interferometry. The specimen grating of 300 lines/mm was replicated on the specimen free edge surface as shown in Fig.3 [5]. This specimen grating deformed together with the specimen when the load was applied.

Fig.3 Dimensions of the CFRP-DCB specimen tested

A two-beam moire interferometry setup was employed to generate a reference grating of 600 lines/mm. These reference gratings were made to interfere with the first-order diffracted light from the specimen grating. Detailed description of moire interferometry appears in Ref.6. Moire fringes were recorded when a crack was arrested and the applied load became stable. Figure 4 shows typical moire fringe patterns associated with the crack opening displacement in the DCB specimen. These fringes were used to determine the values of COD as a function of distance from a crack tip.

Fig.4 Moire fringe patterns of the DCB specimen

3.2. Crack Opening Displacement (COD)

To examine the validity of the present COD analysis, comparison was made with the experimental data obtained from moire interferometry. Such a comparison is shown in Fig.5, where the experimental COD data are indicated by solid marks as a function of the crack length. The solid line shows the COD profile predicted by eq.(7) using the axial modulus $E_1=117\text{Gpa}$ experimentally determined. The result given in Fig.5 shows that the cantilever beam model is clearly inadequate, since eq.(7) yielded much lower COD values than the experimental result.

Because λ must be related to material properties of the fracture process zone ahead of the crack front, it should be determined experimentally. However, the experimental determination is difficult. In the present work, to evaluate λ , a number of trial computations were performed on eq.(6) for values of λ which were systematically changed. Although the computed results were somewhat sensitive to the choice of λ , it is shown in Fig.5 that eq.(6) for $\lambda=316(1/\text{m})$ excellently represents the COD profile for the DCB specimen tested.

Fig.5 Values of COD as a function of the crack length a

3.3. Specimen compliance (C)

Using the trial computational procedure stated above, values of λ were determined as a function of crack length (see Fig.6). The average value of λ was employed for eq.(10) to evaluate the specimen compliance C and to examine the effect of the material stiffness ahead of the crack front. The result is represented in Fig.7 as a function of cubed crack length a^3 , where comparisons are made with the two results predicted by eq.(11) and experimentally determined by

$$C_{EXP} = \delta_{EXP}/P \quad (14)$$

where δ_{EXP} is a crack opening displacement measured at the loading point. In contrast to the cantilever beam result, Fig.7 shows that the present analysis gives very good agreement with the experimental data over a wide range of crack length.

Fig.6 Values of the material stiffness λ ahead of the crack tip

Fig.7 Specimen compliance C as a function of cubed crack length a^3

3.4. Fracture Toughness (G_I)

An important part of this analysis is to clarify a relationship between the fracture toughness and the material stiffness ahead of a crack front. This attempt was made using eq.(12) and values of λ given by Fig.6. The computed results are plotted in Fig.8 as a function of crack length, where a comparison is made with the results predicted by eq.(13). If the value of λ is large enough, eq.(12) would give a fracture toughness value which is almost identical to the one predicted by eq.(13). As can be readily seen from Fig.8, however, the present analysis yielded appreciably larger values of fracture toughness than the built-in cantilever beam analysis. This suggests that the material deformability ahead of the crack front is important in increasing the values of fracture toughness.

Fig.8 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_I as a function of crack length a

4. CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model was presented for analyzing the crack opening displacement (COD) of a DCB specimen. The COD solution was compared with experimental results determined by moire interferometry to evaluate the material stiffness (λ) ahead of the crack front. Using the present solutions, the effects of λ on the specimen compliance (C) and the fracture toughness (G_I) were studied, and the following conclusions were obtained;

- (1) The built-in cantilever beam analysis yielded much smaller COD values than the experiments.
- (2) The solution (6) can predict the experimental COD values in the vicinity of the crack tip.
- (3) For the infinite value of λ , i.e. $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, the solutions obtained are identical to the cantilever beam relationships.
- (4) For finite values of λ , the present analysis gives larger values of COD, C and G_I than the cantilever beam analysis.

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